

D5.2

Validation of thermal comfort, IEQ, productivity and health in hybridGEOTABS buildings

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Summary

This deliverable documents the validation of thermal comfort, IEQ, productivity and health in hybridGEOTABS buildings. The central question is if significant differences can be found between subjects exposed to the indoor environment in hybridGEOTABS buildings with and without Model Predictive Control (MPC). For that, several case study buildings have been selected which were operated using both Rule Based Control (RBC) and MPC.

D5.1 includes a comprehensive literature review on comfort, health and productivity effects of low-temperature radiant systems. According to this review, although limited, there is evidence that radiant systems provide better thermal comfort than all-air systems. However, a direct comparison is generally difficult since radiant systems must be coupled with ventilation systems to control air quality, which affects both the thermal environment and the indoor air quality. Due to their nature, it was recommended that general indices only are insufficient to categorize the indoor environmental quality (IEQ) created by radiant systems. As thermal discomfort was found to affect peoples' ability to concentrate thus reducing productivity, local discomfort indices (vertical temperature difference, temperature drifts) and both thermal sensation and comfort should also be included in the evaluation. CO₂ levels and sick building syndrome (SBS) symptoms must also be investigated. Moreover, it is important to evaluate both transient and long-term effects and examine combined effects of local discomfort indices and general ones such as operative temperature using large datasets of occupant responses.

The experimental results from D5.2 and D5.3 considered the recommendations of the literature review (D5.1) and had the aim of assessing the performance of the hybridGEOTABS buildings. Therefore, the first objective was to categorize the indoor environmental quality in the buildings no matter the control. On top of that, the buildings' performance differences between the two controls implemented, MPC and RBC, were investigated. Therefore, the IEQ was monitored through measurements (based on indoor climate measurements performed in WP4) and IEQ perception was monitored by subjective occupant evaluation (questionnaires conducted in different seasons to account for seasonal effects) for extensive periods of time. Additionally, local discomfort indicators such as vertical temperature difference and temperature drifts were added to general indicators (operative temperature, relative humidity). The questionnaires yielded data on self-perceived effects on sensation, comfort, and acceptability of both temperature and lighting conditions. Moreover, sick building symptoms are assessed.

Overall, the indoor environmental quality was rated as medium for all buildings investigated no matter the control employed. Deviations to moderate and low were observed for short periods of time in the thermal environment. Nevertheless, these could also be because of the default control set points and the changes made by the occupants. Additionally, the indoor air quality was rated as high as the CO₂ concentration was always below the recommended limits.

Although the MPC was active for limited periods of time, it was determined that no significant differences were observed in the IEQ and IEQ perception on a whole-body level from the measurements. However, in the Infrax office building local body parts felt slightly (but statistically significant) cooler in the MPC scenario than in the RBC scenario. Finally, no significant issues were observed in the indoor thermal environment, vertical temperature difference, temperature fluctuations, and indoor air quality measurements for the investigated period.

Discrepancies were observed across the investigated buildings throughout the questionnaires. Although in general, indoor air quality was rated as fresh, in the school the pupils were dissatisfied with the indoor air quality in one of the two classrooms. In the office buildings, the occupants were satisfied with the noise levels, light brightness and colour. However, large variances were registered in terms of sick building syndromes and productivity. Cool sensations on feet were observed during summer/cooling season which could be due to the low temperature setpoint during the same period. Therefore according to the standards and the feedback from

the occupants the indoor thermal environment and comfort can still be improved by tuning the control objectives.

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Nomenclature

Acronyms

AHU	Air Handling Unit
MPC	Model Predictive Control
PMV	Predicted Mean Vote
PPD	Predicted Percentage Dissatisfied
RBC	Rule Based Control
SBS	Sick Building Syndrome
SD	Standard Deviation
TA	Thermal Acceptance
TCV	Thermal Comfort Vote
TP	Thermal Preference
TSV	Thermal Sensation Vote
VAV	Variable Air Volume
CO	Corner office
OP	Open Plan office
RA	Reception Area
RO	Reception Office

Symbols

T_{air}	Air temperature	°C
T_{op}	Operative temperature	°C
RH	Relative humidity	%

1 Introduction

Deliverables 5.2 and 5.3 are reported in this combined report, because D5.2 and D5.3 are highly interconnected in terms of methodology and analysis. Where D5.2 focuses on thermal sensation and comfort, D5.3 studies health and productivity effects. The central question in both D5.2 and D5.3 is if significant differences can be found between subjects exposed to the indoor environment in hybridGEOTABS buildings with and without Model Predictive Control (MPC). For that, several case study buildings have been selected.

Data acquisition in D5.2 and D5.3 is based on physical measurements and questionnaires. The questionnaires were conducted in different seasons to account for seasonal effects. The questionnaires yielded data on self-perceived effects on sensation, comfort, and acceptability of temperature, air quality, lighting conditions, and acoustical conditions. Moreover, sick building symptoms have been assessed as indicators for Health; alertness, concentration and work effort were used as indicators for Productivity. The indoor environmental analysis is based on the validation plan presented in D4.3. Moreover, D4.12 complements the findings presented in this deliverable by providing results on energy, environment and cost.

D5.1 includes a comprehensive literature review on comfort, health and productivity effects of low-temperature radiant systems. The experimental results from D5.2 and D5.3 will be compared to the insights from the literature review (D5.1).

Reading instructions

Chapter 2 provides a comprehensive description of the methodology for data acquisition including (i) the case study buildings, (ii) the indoor environmental measurements, and (iii) the questionnaires. Chapter 3 elaborates on the methodology for analysis including the used Performance Indicators for IEQ analysis and subjective data analysis from the questionnaires. Chapter 4 presents the results of Solarwind case study, Chapter 5 on Líbeznice, Chapter 6 on Ter Potterie, Chapter 7 on Infrax.

2 Methodology: case study buildings, measurements and questionnaires

Indoor measurements and questionnaires were conducted in three case study buildings. Although the buildings analysed in this study already have advanced Building Management Systems (BMS), a more detailed measurement plan was used for the purposes of documenting the current performance of their HVAC systems regarding the thermal indoor environment, and to be able to study the improvements after the implementation of the MPC. The methodology behind the field measurements was described in the works of Kazanci et al. [1] and is presented in the following subchapters.

2.1 Case-study buildings

Four case study buildings have been selected, see Figure 1, that appear in the following order in this report:

- 1) Solarwind office building in Windhof (LU)
- 2) Elementary school in Libeznice (CZ)
- 3) 'Ter Potterie' Elderly home in Bruges (BE)
- 4) Infracx office building in Dilbeek (BE)

This chapter provides a short description of the buildings' construction and HVAC systems in the context of the indoor environment. A detailed and technical documentation of the buildings (incl. hydraulic schemes, operational modes, controls etc) is provided in [D4.11](#).

Figure 1: Pictures of the case-study buildings (From left to right - top: Infracx, Libeznice School, bottom: Solarwind, Ter Potterie).

Figure 2. Pictures of the case-study buildings' interior (From left to right - top: Infrac, Libeznice School, bottom: Solarwind, Ter Potterie).

2.1.1 Solarwind office building

Solarwind is at the forefront of sustainable construction in Luxembourg, achieving triple environmental certification. The building envelope, solar orientation, materials and triple glazing were designed for energy efficiency. The Solarwind building is a very well-insulated and airtight building fabric designed following the passive house standards (envelope U-value $0.16 \text{ W/m}^2 \cdot \text{K}$, glazing U-value $0.69 \text{ W/m}^2 \cdot \text{K}$). It has a moderate glazing area of about 24% with triple glazed windows and movable shading blinds (on the exterior in the east and west, and in the interior in north and south), combined with fixed shading elements that carry the photovoltaics on the main (south) façade.

Heating and cooling are delivered via concrete core activation mainly via the ceiling, coupled with heat pumps in the winter and passive cooling in the summer, optimizing energy use and reducing maintenance costs. In about 5% of the zones a chilled ceiling provides cooling. Secondary heating emission happens via (dependent on the zones and functions) radiators and the air handling unit (AHU).

The Solarwind building is well ventilated (ID2), utilizing a dual heat exchanger and adiabatic cooling. The mechanical ventilation system adapts ventilation flows automatically with input from the air quality sensors that monitor the occupancy flow of the building. Other renewable energy sources used include urban wind turbines, solar photovoltaic & thermal, and biomass wood pellets for hot water production. Other features include rainwater harvesting for adiabatic cooling and toilet flushing, motion detectors and brightness sensors for lighting, a green roof facade and a 'zero bin concept'.

2.1.2 Libeznice school building

The school in Libeznice is a $1,000 \text{ m}^2$ elementary school in the Central Bohemian Region of the Czech Republic. It consists of nine classrooms and ancillary rooms arranged in a striking circular 'doughnut' shape around a central play area. It accommodates 270 pupils. The U-values for the outer walls, floor and roof are on average $0.27 \text{ W/(m}^2 \cdot \text{K)}$. There are three windows and one exterior door in each class. The windows have double glazing with a

U-value of $1.2 \text{ W}/(\text{m}^2\cdot\text{K})$. The windows are equipped with blinds that can be dropped down manually. Certain areas of the ceilings are covered by hanging acoustic sound absorbers.

TABS is the main heating and cooling system implemented only in the ceiling slab. Heating and cooling are supplied to the building via geothermal energy fed via a Ground Source Heat Pump from six boreholes. Independent low-temperature ventilation units provide fresh air to each classroom and supplement the TABS. The system is controlled by a model predictive controller that considers the weather forecast, spot market electricity prices, and the thermodynamic models of the heat pump and TABS.

2.1.3 Ter Potterie elderly home

Ter Potterie is a care home in Bruges, Belgium, completed in 2016. It consists of 121 rooms, nursing stations, living room/lounge areas, bathrooms and storage areas, surrounding a central garden area. The elderly home is a very energy demanding building as it has a constant occupation rate (24/7) with a relatively high ambient temperature and consumption of domestic hot water. Space heating is delivered by a geothermal system linked to a heat pump. The U-values for the outer walls and floors rate between 0.25 and $0.27 \text{ W}/\text{m}^2\cdot\text{K}$. The flat and sloped roofs have a U-value of $0.25 \text{ W}/\text{m}^2\cdot\text{K}$ and $0.16 \text{ W}/\text{m}^2\cdot\text{K}$, respectively. The windows have a U-value of $1.69 \text{ W}/\text{m}^2\cdot\text{K}$ and are provided with double glazing at a U-value of $1.1 \text{ W}/(\text{m}^2\cdot\text{K})$. The HVAC system and shading are controlled A weather station is installed to measure the outdoor environment with the goal to control the HVAC systems and shading.

The building's concrete core activation is utilised for both heating and cooling while the ventilation system removes part of the load during the cooling season. Passive cooling is utilized in the cooling season (cooling provided to TABS, floor circuit and the cooling coils in AHUs). The AHU and (central mechanical ventilation system with supply, exhaust, and heat recovery) and radiators installed in all rooms meet the residual load. Nevertheless, the ground floor is conditioned using both radiators and floor heating/cooling.

2.1.4 Infrac office building

Infrac is a $3,662 \text{ m}^2$ office building in Dilbeek, Belgium, with kitchen, cafeteria, server cooling rooms, and parking. The U-values for the outer walls and roof are between 0.18 - 0.25 and 0.14 - $0.15 \text{ W}/\text{m}^2\cdot\text{K}$, respectively. The windows have double glazing with a U-value of $1.0 \text{ W}/\text{m}^2\cdot\text{K}$. Daylight sensors dim the artificial lighting during periods of sufficient daylight in order to limit the internal heat gains. The building also features a large solar photovoltaic array and solar gains are reduced by screens or overhangs over windows. A cooling tower is present for the server rooms.

Heating and cooling are delivered by two geothermal heat pumps through a TABS system and heat exchangers within the AHU. The heating and cooling demands are mostly met by TABS located in the floor slabs while the temperature is fine tuned to the desired level by pre-cooling or pre-heating the ventilation air supplied through variable air volume (VAV) boxes.

2.2 Measurement equipment

Air and globe temperatures were measured with TMCx-HD temperature sensors. Air and globe temperature sensors had an accuracy of $\pm 0.2^\circ\text{C}$ within the temperature ranges expected in indoor environments (i.e. 10 - 30°C). The output from the air and globe temperature sensors were logged with portable data loggers. These portable data loggers were HOBO U12-013 (two external channels, and integrated temperature and relative humidity sensors) and HOBO UX120-006M (four external channels, no integrated measurement devices).

Air temperature sensors were shielded from the radiation effects by a metal cylinder placed around them. Globe temperatures were measured with a matt grey globe sensor, 40 mm in diameter. This sensor has the same

relative influence of air- and mean radiant temperature as on a person and, thus, at 0.6 and 1.1 m heights will represent the operative temperature of a sedentary or a standing person, respectively.

CO₂ concentration was measured with a Vaisala GMW22 sensor and its output was logged with a HOBO U12-012 (one external channel, and integrated temperature, relative humidity, and light intensity sensors). The CO₂ sensor had an accuracy of ± 100 ppm + 2% of reading, within the range of 0-5000 ppm.

Window opening and closing behavior was monitored with a HOBO UX90-001 state logger and a magnet placed on the windows.

Surface temperatures were measured with iButtons (DS1922L), which had an accuracy of $\pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ within the range of -10°C to 65°C .

Relative humidity was measured either with a HOBO U12-013 or with a HOBO U12-012. Relative humidity measurements had an accuracy of $\pm 2.5\%$, within the range of 10-90% RH.

All sensors were calibrated prior to installation in the buildings. Data logging interval was 10 minutes for all measurements.

2.3 Measurements in the office building Solarwind in Windhof, LU

For the Solarwind building, the office space of the building owner was selected for the measurements. The measurement locations were selected to capture the different room types and orientations. The selected measurement locations were a small open plan office (reception area), a two-person office next to the reception area, a corner office (two-persons), and a large open plan office.

A measurement stand (Figure 3) was placed in each of these four areas (measurement locations). Air and globe temperatures were measured at 0.1 m (ankle level), 0.6 m (center of the body for a seated person), 1.1 m (head level for a seated person and center of the body for a standing person) and 1.7 m (head level for a standing person) heights on this stand according to recommendations given by EN ISO 7726.

Figure 3. The measurement stand used in a measurement location in the office building [1].

Another sensor on the same stand (at 1.3 m height) was measuring the CO₂ concentration. The CO₂ concentration is intended to be used as an indicator for the air quality and to evaluate the performance of the ventilation system. Relative humidity was also measured on this stand. At the same location as the stand, ceiling and floor surface temperatures were measured, since in buildings with TABS, indoor spaces are heated and cooled through these surfaces. These surface temperatures could also be used to calculate the mean radiant temperature.

2.4 Measurements in elderly home (Ter Potterie) in Bruges, BE

In the elderly home, there are single rooms, which consist of a living area with a bed, and a bathroom. These rooms are identical. There is also possibility for couples to live in two rooms ("double room"), which then one room becomes the living room and the other room becomes the bedroom (both of these rooms have bathrooms). There are also common living areas, where the occupants can spend time during the day and interact with other occupants.

For the measurements in the elderly home, sensors were installed in two single rooms, in a double room (in the living room and in the bedroom) and in a common living area. The measurements carried out in the common living area was similar to the measurement strategy described for the office room (a measurement stand with air and globe temperature sensors and a CO₂ concentration sensor, and ceiling and floor surface temperatures).

The measurement strategy followed in the other rooms (two single rooms and a double room) were identical to each other. In these rooms, it was not possible to use the same measurement stand due to safety concerns. Therefore, a smaller stand was built. This stand consisted of the structural part, a portable data logger, and the air and the globe temperature sensors. In each room, there were two of these small stands placed in the positions where the occupants were expected to be (e.g. close to their bed, next to their chair, etc.).

In each room, there were two operable windows (one large and one small). The opening and closing state of these windows were logged along with CO₂ concentration and relative humidity. In addition to the logged floor and ceiling surface temperatures in the rooms, radiator surface temperature in the middle of the radiator was also logged. This measurement could help in setting up the energy balance of the rooms for manual calculations or for dynamic building simulations, and to identify the occupant preferences and behavior.

Figure 4 shows the measurement stand used in the common living area and the small stand built for the measurements in the elderly home.

a)

b)

Figure 4. a) The measurement stand used in the common living area, b) The small stand built for the measurements in the elderly home [1].

2.5 Measurements in the elementary school in Libeznice, CZ

In the elementary school, two identical classrooms were selected for the measurements. The measurement strategy followed in the two classrooms were identical.

There were two stands (measuring air and globe temperatures at 0.1, 0.6 and 1.1 m heights) positioned close to a wall (0.3 m away from the wall). This was not the optimal positioning; however, it was not possible to place the stands in a more central position in the classrooms due to safety concerns.

In addition to this, on the opposite side of the classroom, air and globe temperature sensors were placed on the wall (slightly sticking out from the wall and at 1.25 m height corresponding to approximately the same height as the BMS sensor). This was done in order to compare the temperature measurements in the opposite sides of the classroom and to compare the temperature measurements with the measurements from the BMS sensor.

Relative humidity and CO₂ concentration were also measured in the classrooms. However, the latter was not measured on the stands due to wiring limitations.

Since this building had TABS only in the ceiling slab, the surface temperatures were measured only on the ceiling. The surface temperatures were measured at two points. One surface temperature was measured on a point that was facing the room directly and the second surface temperature was measured on a point that was covered by one of the hanging acoustic sound absorbers. This was done to be able to study the effects of acoustic sound absorbers on the heat transfer between the activated ceiling surface and the classroom.

Figure 5 shows the measurement stand used in the classrooms and the surface temperature measurements on the ceiling.

Figure 5. a) The measurement stand used in the classrooms, b) Surface temperature measurement on the ceiling surface facing the room, c) Surface temperature measurement on the ceiling surface covered by the acoustic sound absorber [1].

2.6 Measurements in the office building Infracx

In the Infracx building three measurement stands (Figure 6) were placed which measured air and globe temperatures at 0.1 m (ankle level), 0.6 m (center of the body for a seated person), 1.1 m (head level for a seated person and center of the body for a standing person) and 1.7 m (head level for a standing person) heights on this stand according to recommendations given by EN ISO 7726. The selected measurement locations were the reception desk on the second floor, and at two work desks in the open-plan office at the third floor. In the open-plan office, CO₂ concentration and relative humidity were measured as well on the stands at a height of 1.3 m. Ceiling surface temperature was measured at all three locations in the building above the stand.

Figure 6. Placement example of measurement stand Infracx building.

2.7 Questionnaires at Solarwind and Infracx offices

Questionnaires were used to assess the self-perceived effects of the indoor environment in the demo-buildings.

The most extensive questionnaires were conducted in the Solarwind and Infracx office buildings. These questionnaires were conducted using an online survey tool built in-house by the research group TherMU at Maastricht University. The full questionnaire is included in Annex 5 Questionnaire templates (separate documents).

Table 1 and Table 2 show the number of conducted questionnaires at Solarwind and Infracx, respectively.

Table 1. Number of conducted questionnaires at Solarwind office building.

	Season			
	Spring	Summer	Autumn	Winter
Rule Based Control	30	90	61	58
Model Predictive Control	-	-	-	-

Table 2. Number of conducted questionnaires at Infrac office building.

	Season			
	Spring	Summer	Autumn	Winter
Rule Based Control	0	0	62	99
Model Predictive Control	0	0	153	27

Table 3 shows an overview of studied items and used performance indicators in the questionnaires. Besides, the listed items, some questionnaires yield data on Gender, Clothing and Transportation mode.

Table 3 Overview of studied items and used performance indicators.

Item	Performance indicators
IEQ / Thermal sensation	Thermal sensation vote (whole body and local parts)
IEQ / Thermal comfort	Thermal comfort vote (whole body and local parts)
IEQ / Thermal preference	Thermal preference vote
IEQ / Comfort related to air movement	Thermal comfort vote (whole body and local parts)
IEQ / Comfort related to air movement	Preference (whole body and local parts)
IEQ quality / IAQ	Windows openable
IEQ quality / IAQ	Air quality acceptability
IEQ quality / IAQ	Air stuffiness
IEQ quality / acoustic	Noise acceptability
IEQ quality / light	Light control modes
IEQ quality / light	Light color comfort level
IEQ quality / light	Light brightness comfort level
Health	Headache
Health	Nose irritation
Health	Throat irritation
Health	Fatigue
Health	Dry eyes
Productivity	Concentration
Productivity	Alertness
Productivity	Task effort
Productivity	Task performance

2.8 Questionnaires at Ter Potterie elderly home

The questionnaires are paper-based (the questionnaires have been physically distributed to the elderly). The questionnaires have been conducted in the area indicated with the red circle in Figure 7 as we have a good overview of the thermal conditions in that area. Within the area in the red circle, there are 27 rooms and two common areas, and a room where some nurses are. The nurses ask, help and guide the elderly to fill in the questionnaires and then collect them.

After the completion of the questionnaires for that season (month), the nurses scan and email/send the questionnaires to DTU.

Figure 7 First floor of Ter Potterie. Highlighted areas are measurement locations.

The full questionnaire is included in Annex 5 Questionnaire templates (separate document).

Table 4 shows the number of conducted questionnaires at Ter Potterie.

Table 4. Number of conducted questionnaires at Ter Potterie.

	Season			
	Spring	Summer	Autumn	Winter
Rule Based Control	221	195	321	139
Model Predictive Control	-	-	18	-

Table 5 shows an overview of studied items and used performance indicators in the questionnaires. Besides, the listed items, questionnaires yield data on Age, Gender and Clothing.

Table 5 Overview of studied items and used performance indicators.

Item	Performance indicators
IEQ / Thermal sensation	Thermal sensation vote (whole body and local parts)
IEQ / Thermal comfort	Thermal comfort vote (whole body and local parts)
IEQ / Thermal preference	Thermal preference vote
IEQ quality / IAQ	Air quality acceptability
IEQ quality / IAQ	Air stuffiness
IEQ quality / acoustic	Noise acceptability
IEQ quality / light	Light brightness comfort level

2.9 Questionnaires at Libeznice

The questionnaires were paper-based (the questionnaires have been physically distributed to the pupils) in the beginning. The questionnaires have been conducted in classrooms 2B (Neptun) and 2D (Jupiter) indicated in Figure 8. Both classrooms housed 15 pupils each. The teachers asked, helped and guided the pupils to fill in the questionnaires and then collected them.

After the completion of the questionnaires for that season (month), the teachers scanned and emailed/sent the questionnaires to DTU. However, it turned out that this method was too labour intensive, so simplified online questionnaires were used instead and yielded much more responses. The school never operated on RBC, but went into operation immediately on MPC. However, the original MPC version has been upgraded during the project. All online questionnaires have been conducted during the upgraded version of MPC.

Figure 8. Floorplan of Libeznice elementary school. Questionnaires have been conducted in classrooms 2B (Neptun) and 2D (Jupiter).

Annex 5 Questionnaire templates includes: (i) the hard copy English version including transcription that was used in the beginning; (ii) an example of a filled in questionnaire in Czech language; (iii) the online version of the questionnaires. The hard copy questionnaires turned out to be too labour intensive for the teachers (only 61 completed questionnaires), and hence, we switched to a simplified online version.

Table 6 shows the number of online conducted questionnaires at Libeznice elementary school. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, we stopped conducting questionnaires from March 2020 onwards. The school was closed in Spring and reopened in Summer. However, the pupils had to wear masks which may alter the perception of the environment regarding thermal perception and IAQ perception. Moreover, teachers preferred to discontinue the field study. Therefore, the decision was made to stop the IEQ measurements and questionnaires at Libeznice elementary school.

Table 6. Number of conducted questionnaires (dd. 7 July 2020) at Libeznice elementary school.

	Season			
	Spring	Summer	Autumn	Winter
Rule Based Control	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.
Model Predictive Control	426	463	-	-

Table 7 shows an overview of studied items and used performance indicators in the questionnaires. Besides, the listed items, questionnaires yield data on Gender.

Table 7 Overview of studied items and used performance indicators.

Item	Performance indicators
IEQ / Thermal sensation	Thermal sensation vote (whole body)
IEQ / Thermal comfort	Thermal comfort vote (whole body)
IEQ quality / IAQ	Air stuffiness
Metabolic rate	Recent activity (sitting or running)

3 Methodology: performance indicators

The methodology for the indoor environment quality (IEQ) physical measurements, long and short-term, plus questionnaires for the presented buildings is described in Chapter 2. The parameters were measured by dedicated sensors following the guidelines presented in standards. The acquired data was compared to the limits presented in this chapter. The theory, limits and methodology behind the planned measurements are based on standards specialized on the indoor environment: ASHRAE 55-2017 and EN16798-1:2019[2][3]. Recently, an extensive review of these standards was published, which presents more detailed information on the matter [4].

The IEQ investigation was made based on different categories of indoor environmental quality for IEQ performance indicators defined by EN 16798:1-2019. The categories are presented in Table 8.

Table 8. Categories of indoor environmental quality [3].

Category	Level of expectation
I	High
II	Medium
III	Moderate
IV	Low

The categories visible in Table 8 are related to the level of expectations the occupants may have for a building, zone or specific room. According to EN 16798:1-2019, a normal level is considered as “Medium”, thus category II. A higher level such as category I could be necessary for occupants with special needs (children, elderly, persons with disabilities, etc.) with low metabolic rate and impaired control of body temperature. Categories III and IV represent spaces without any health risk but may decrease comfort [3].

3.1 Physical measurements

3.1.1 Thermal environment

Thermal environment measurements were made where occupants are known to spend most of their time. Additionally, measurements were acquired for several years to obtain data for a representative period under weather conditions of both the cold and warm season as well as transitioning periods as suggested by standards.

The following definitions for certain terms, provided by ASHRAE 55-2017, EN 16798-1:2019 and ISO 7730:2006, are relevant in the scope of indoor thermal environment:

- **“metabolic rate (met):** the rate of transformation of chemical energy into heat and mechanical work by metabolic activities of an individual, per unit of skin surface area (expressed in units of met) equal to 58.2 W/m² (18.4 Btu/h·ft²), which is the energy produced per unit skin surface area of an average person seated at rest” [2].
- **“clo:** a unit used to express the thermal insulation provided by garments and clothing ensembles; 1 clo = 0.155 m²°C/W [2]”
- **“operative temperature:** uniform temperature of an imaginary black enclosure in which an occupant would exchange the same amount of heat by radiation plus convection as in the actual non-uniform environment” [3]

- **“optimal operative temperature:** – operative temperature that satisfies the greatest percentage of occupants at a given clothing and activity level in the current thermal environment” [3].
- **“Predicted Mean Vote (PMV):** the mean value of the thermal votes of a large group of people exposed to the same environment” [5].
- **“Percentage of People Dissatisfied (PPD):** an index that establishes a quantitative prediction of the percentage of thermally dissatisfied people who feel too cool or too warm” [5].
- **“draft:** the unwanted local cooling of the body caused by air movement” [2].
- **“local thermal discomfort:** the thermal discomfort caused by locally specific conditions such as a vertical air temperature difference between the feet and the head, by radiant temperature asymmetry, by local convective cooling (draft), or by contact with a hot or cold floor” [2].

Operative temperature limits and measurements

The buildings analyzed are mechanically heated/cooled buildings. Therefore, the upper and lower limits for both winter and summer seasons for the operative temperature based on PMV-PPD thermal comfort indices suggested by standards EN 16798-1:2019 were used. These limits based on the aforementioned categories are visible in Table 9. For the heating and cooling season, the operative temperature limits are defined for a clothing level of ~1.0 clo and ~0.5 clo, respectively.

Table 9. Operative temperature ranges for heating and cooling seasons for buildings with mechanical cooling systems [3].

Type of building or space	Category	Temperature range for heating seasons °C	Temperature range for cooling seasons °C
		~1.0 clo	~0.5 clo
Residential buildings, living space (bed rooms, kitchens, living rooms etc.) ~1.2 met	I	21.0-25.0	23.5-25.5
	II	20.0-25.0	23.0-26.0
	III	18.0-25.0	22.0-27.0
	IV	17.0-25.0	21.0-27.0
Offices and spaces with similar activity (single offices, open plan offices, conference rooms, auditoria, cafeteria, restaurants, class rooms) ~1.2 met	I	21.0-23.0	23.5-25.5
	II	20.0-24.0	23.0-26.0
	III	19.0-25.0	22.0-27.0
	IV	17.0-25.0	21.0-28.0

However, the standards do not define operative temperature limits for the transitioning periods, i.e. periods between the heating and cooling season. Therefore, by assuming a clothing level of ~0.75 clo, operative temperature limits were calculated based on the PMV-PPD thermal comfort indices using the CBE Thermal Comfort Tool [6]. Table 10 provides the limits for all seasons (heating, cooling, and transition periods) for both investigated building types. In the table, the colour scheme used in the rest of the report for the IEQ categories is visible.

Table 10. Operative temperature limits for the heating, cooling, and transition periods.

Type of building or space	Category	Heating Season °C	Cooling Season °C	Transition periods °C
		~1.0 clo	~0.5 clo	~0.75 clo
Residential buildings, living space (bed rooms, kitchens, living rooms etc.) ~1.2 met	I	21-25	23.5-25.5	23-24.5
	II	20-25	23-26	21.5-25.5
	III	18-25	22-27	21-26.5
	IV	17-25	21-28	19.5-27.5
Offices and spaces with similar activity (single offices, open plan offices, conference rooms, auditoria, cafeteria, restaurants, class rooms) ~1.2 met	I	21-23	23.5-25.5	23-24.5
	II	20-24	23-26	22-25.5
	III	19-25	22-27	21-26
	IV	17-25	21-28	20-27.5

Local thermal discomfort

Local thermal discomfort is a thermal dissatisfaction of the occupant caused by unwanted cooling or heating of one particular part of the body, abnormally high vertical temperature difference between head and ankles, by too warm or too cool floor or by a high radiant temperature asymmetry [5]. Table 11 provides local thermal discomfort criteria only for vertical air temperature difference and range of floor temperature in accordance with the proposed measurements for different categories.

Table 11. Local thermal discomfort for vertical air temperature difference and range of floor temperature based on categories [3].

	Vertical air temperature difference head (1.1 m) and ankle (0.1 m)		Range of floor temperature	
	PD [%]	Temperature Difference [K]	PD [%]	Floor surface temperature range [°C]
CAT I	3	2	10	19 to 29
CAT II	5	3	10	19 to 29
CAT III	10	4	15	17 to 31

Drifts or Ramps

According to ASHRAE 55-2017 [2] when occupants do not have direct control over the temperature, requirements with respect to temperature variations in time should be met. Drifts and ramps, monotonic, noncyclic changes in operative temperature and cyclic variations with a period greater than 15 minutes shall not exceed the requirements listed in Table 12 .

Table 12. Limits on temperature drifts and ramps [2].

Time period [h]	0.25	0.5	1	2	4
Maximum operative temperature change allowed [°C]	1.1	1.7	2.2	2.8	3.3

3.1.2 Indoor air quality

EN 16798-1:2019 [3] expresses indoor air quality as the required level of ventilation or CO₂ concentration. Thus, CO₂ can be used as an indicator in buildings where people represent the main pollution sources such as the investigated buildings in this study. The required ventilation (or CO₂ level) is based on health and comfort criteria. In most cases the health criteria will also be met by the required ventilation for comfort (perceived air quality). As the concentration of one source is reduced through air change, the concentration of others will also be reduced. Therefore, health risks are reduced by providing sufficient ventilation to meet the requirements of certain pollutants such as CO₂.

As described by the same standard [3], measurements should be made where occupants are known to spend most of their time, preferably at head level during typical high load conditions. CO₂ measurements should cover winter conditions, as fresh air supply is normally lowest during the colder months due to the limited use of operable windows and partly closed façade shutters due to draft risk. Finally, measurements done only in representative rooms could be enough with respect to larger buildings and thus not all rooms need to be evaluated.

Table 13. Default design concentrations above outdoor concentration assuming a standard CO₂ emission of 20 L/(h/person) [3].

Category	Corresponding CO ₂ concentration above outdoors in PPM for non-adapted persons [ppm]
I	550
II	800
III	1350
IV	1350

The values in Table 13 correspond to the equilibrium concentration when the air flow rate is 10, 7, and 4 l/s per person for CAT I, II and III, IV respectively and the CO₂ emission is 20 l/h per person. The default outside average concentration can be assumed to 400 ppm (350 ppm to 500 ppm). Therefore, when evaluating 400 ppm or a more appropriate value depending on the location of the building should be added to each value in Table 13 [3].

3.1.3 Relative humidity

According to ASHRAE 55-2017, humidity represents “a general reference to the moisture content of the air. It is expressed in terms of several thermodynamic variables, including vapor pressure, dew-point temperature, wetbulb temperature, humidity ratio, and relative humidity. It is spatially and temporally averaged in the same manner as air temperature” [2].

The humidity criteria depend partly on the requirements for thermal comfort and indoor air quality as it influences both and partly on the physical requirements of the building (condensation, mould growth etc.). Humidification or dehumidification is usually not required but, if used, excess humidification and dehumidification shall be avoided [3].

Table 14. Recommended humidity levels in occupied spaces [3].

Category	Design humidity relative for dehumidification [%]	Design humidity relative for humidification [%]
I	50	30
II	60	25
III	70	20

3.2 Other measurements

Other measurements can represent spot measurements, which, as Kazanci et al. [1] points out, could consist of measurements of air velocity, turbulence intensity and air temperature (which will then allow determination of the draft rate), radiant temperature asymmetry, noise and lighting level. Spot measurements allow focusing on the most problematic areas (where occupants have complaints). The results will be analyzed according to the limits available in EN 16798-1:2019 for local thermal discomfort (Table 15) with respect to the aforementioned categories. Additionally, window opening and closing behavior can be monitored which could help explain certain unexpected conditions due to the occupants’ behaviour in the data acquired.

Table 15. Local thermal discomfort for draft and radiant temperature asymmetry according to categories [3].

	Draft			Radiant temperature asymmetry				
	DR (Draft Rate) [%]	Maximum air velocity [m/s]		PD [%]	Warm ceiling [K]	Cool wall [K]	Cool ceiling [K]	Warm wall [K]
		Winter	Summer					
I	10	0.10	0.12	5	< 5	< 10	< 14	< 23
II	20	0.16	0.19	5	< 5	< 10	< 14	< 23
III	30	0.21	0.24	10	< 7	< 13	< 18	< 35

3.3 Questionnaires

Questionnaires are aimed at analyzing the subjective response of occupants with respect to the IEQ factors (i.e. thermal, air quality, light and acoustics) while also identifying potential problems with respect to health and productivity which could be a consequence of the quality of the indoor environment.

The following definitions for certain terms, provided by ASHRAE 55-2017 are relevant in the scope of understanding questionnaires and their scales:

- **"sensation, thermal:** a conscious subjective expression of an occupant's thermal perception of the environment, commonly expressed using the categories "cold," "cool," "slightly cool", "neutral", "slightly warm", "warm" and "hot"." [2]
- **"comfort, thermal:** that condition of mind that expresses satisfaction with the thermal environment and is assessed by subjective evaluation" [2]
- **"thermal preference:** preference scales for temperature and air movement are also used (e.g., these scales are common in the comfort field study database found in ASHRAE RP-884, Towards an Adaptive Model of Thermal Comfort and Preference [ASHRAE 1998]): "Prefer to be:" "cooler/no change/warmer" "Prefer": "less air movement/no change/more air movement"
- **"thermal comfort due to air movement:** air-movement preference votes ("less" / "no change" / "more")" [2].
- For many other items on the questionnaires, Visual Analog Scales (VAS) were used, such as for alertness, sleepiness etc.
- In the simplified online questionnaire for Libeznice elementary school, the scales have been adapted for the pupils.

3.4 Correlation between measurements and questionnaires

According to Kazanci et al. [1], the responses to the questionnaires (satisfaction with the indoor environment) will be compared to the physical measurements to identify the correlation and the discrepancies between them. The physical measurements (long-term and spot measurements) and the questionnaires will complement each other for obtaining a complete understanding of the indoor environment and user satisfaction in hybridGEOTABS buildings. Moreover, they will offer a performance assessment of the buildings and for creating a link between the indoor environment with system performance and control improvement (Rule Based Control vs. Model Predictive Control).

4 Results: Solarwind offices, Luxembourg

4.1 IEQ and occupants' perception: Thermal environment

4.1.1 Physical measurements

In the Solarwind building, measurements took place in the reception area (RA), the two-person office room next to the reception area (RO), the corner (CO) and the open-plan (OP) office. The IEQ measurements took place over three years, from 2019 to 2020. During the analyzed years a rule based control (RBC) was applied to the operation of the Solarwind building. The indoor environmental parameters measured were: air temperature (T_{air}), operative temperature (T_{op}), relative humidity (RH) and CO₂ concentration.

Each space had multiple sensors which were part of the same stand, thus measuring at multiple heights. Since similar trends were observed between the values measured with differences only due to thermal stratification, only critical information is presented and discussed in this section, while further details are provided in the annex (Annex 1). In the graphs, the operative temperature value measured at a height of 0.6 m is shown. Additionally, details are provided for the operative temperature distribution for the heating and cooling periods. For the analysis, the cooling, heating, and transitioning periods were defined according to the building operation, i.e. heating, cooling, or neutral (transition period) mode. Since Solarwind is an office building, an occupancy schedule from 08:00 to 18:00 was assumed. For the long-term evaluation, the limits defined were the ones recommended by standards EN16798-1:2019 and ASHRAE 55:2017 and summarized in chapter 3. Moreover, the IEQ limits selected from the standards were the ones recommended for offices and spaces with similar activity.

During all investigated years (2018, 2019, and 2020), the time outside the categories recommended by the standards for the operative temperature was limited and close to zero in most instances (Figure 9). Overall, the building registered better indoor environmental conditions during 2018. In 2019 and 2020 the indoor thermal environment registered occupied time with operative temperatures outside the recommended ranges, leading to periods with a Category IV indoor environment - up to 6%. On the other hand, in 2018 the indoor thermal environment was almost all of the time in Category III or better, with 91.5% of the time in Category II on average (for occupants with a medium level of expectation). In 2019 and 2020 the indoor thermal environment during the occupied time reduced to 73% and 66% in Category II or higher, respectively.

According to the operative temperature distribution (Figure 10, Figure 11, and Figure 12), over the heating season, 95% of the operative temperature values were situated within the Category II range (20-24 °C), with slightly higher values in the reception area (RA) and office (RO). However, during the cooling and transition periods, the operative temperature registered values towards the lower limits recommended by the standards over all investigated years. During both the cooling and transition periods approximately 50% of the data was situated below the lower bound of Category II (23.5 °C for cooling and 22 °C during the transition period) with values as low as 20 °C to 22 °C, the lower bounds of Category III during the transition and cooling periods. The values observed suggested that the spaces were generally cooler than recommended by the standards during the transition and cooling periods. Moreover, the smaller variance during the cooling season, especially in 2020 (Figure 12), could indicate a tighter temperature deadband than in the other periods. Therefore, a higher temperature set point during the cooling season could lead to a lower energy use and a better overall indoor thermal environment. Nevertheless, the differences between the recommended limits by the standards and the measured values could be a consequence of the implemented room temperature set point. Although the room temperature set point is implemented by the building manager, it can be modified locally by the occupants depending on their preference, which could explain especially the lower temperatures during the cooling season.

For all the investigated periods, drifts and ramps were registered in the operative temperature during short periods of time (within 30 minutes), however for less than 2% of the occupied time. These fluctuations were

mostly observed in the reception area (RA) which could be due to the nature of the space which might present frequent door openings and changes in the number of occupants. Nevertheless, no visible issues were observed as no sudden or frequent fluctuations outside the allowed limits were present in the operative temperature for the other spaces investigated. The vertical temperature difference between 1.1 and 0.1 (head and ankles of a seated occupant) was almost always less than 2 K, while the floor temperature was within 19 and 29 °C during most of the time (Table 16). As both parameters were within the recommended values by EN 16798-1:2019, the occupants in the investigated rooms were not subject to local thermal discomfort from abnormal vertical temperature or warm/cool floors.

Figure 9. Long-term indoor thermal environment evaluation (2018 and 2019, 2020) – operative temperature (T_{op}) measured in the reception area (RA), reception office (RO), corner office (CO) and the open-plan office (OP) at 0.6 m.

Figure 10. Operative temperature (T_{op}) distribution during occupancy by space – cooling, heating, and transition period, 2018, 0.6 m height.

Figure 11. Operative temperature (T_{op}) distribution during occupancy by space – cooling, heating, and transition period, 2019, 0.6 m height.

Figure 12. Operative temperature (T_{op}) distribution during occupancy by space – cooling, heating, and transition period, 2020, 0.6 m height.

Table 16. Vertical temperature difference (VTD) and Floor temperature range (FTR) for SolarWind (2018 & 2019).

Criteria	Year	Value	Limits EN 16798-1
VTD	2018	97% and above CATI	$\Delta T_{1.1m,0.1m} \leq 2 \text{ K}$
	2019	98% and above CATI	
	2020	98% and above CATI	
FTR	2018	99% and above CATI	$19 \leq T_{floor} \leq 29$
	2019	99% and above CATI	
	2020	99% and above CATI	

The normal local thermal comfort was further enforced by the floor and ceiling surface temperature distribution presented in (Figure 13, Figure 14, and Figure 15). The surface temperature of both the ceiling and the floor was between 20-26 °C with a slightly higher variance in spring and autumn than summer and winter. This could be because of the transition periods which might coincide with the autumn and spring seasons. The general trend observed was a higher temperature in the ceiling’s surface, which suggests a normal thermal stratification over the entire year. Higher temperature ranges were observed for the open plan office (OP) in spring and summer than autumn and winter.

For all three years analyzed, the relative humidity (RH) was within Category II or better (between 25 and 60%) of EN16798-1:2019 for most of the occupied time (more than 90%). Although the time in CATII (between 25 and 60 %) increased in 2020 compared to 2018 and 2019, the RH was within CATIII (between 20 and 70 %) for only a short period of time in all investigated rooms. However, as the Solarwind building is an office building with an expected moderate activity level of less than 2 met and with operative temperatures less than 26 °C (Figure 9 and Figure 12) the influence of humidity was limited on the thermal sensation according to ISO 7730 (e.g. a 10% higher RH is felt as a 0.3 °C rise in the operative temperature).

Figure 13. Floor (fl) and ceiling (cl) surface temperature distribution by season for all investigated rooms, 2018.

Figure 14. Floor (fl) and ceiling (cl) surface temperature distribution by season for all investigated rooms, 2018.

Figure 15. Floor (fl) and ceiling (cl) surface temperature distribution by season for all investigated rooms, 2018.

4.1.2 Questionnaires

The questionnaire data is categorized per season to consider seasonal effects of IEQ variations. Figure 16 shows the ratings of thermal sensation (Left) and thermal comfort (Right) for the RBC scenario. The variance of thermal sensation, which is indicated by the SD, is rather small. The mean is slightly below neutrality indicating that the indoor temperature is slightly low for all seasons. The variance of thermal comfort is larger indicating substantial inter-individual differences, possibly due to differences in age, body composition, or gender. The median comfort is rated as (just) comfortable for all seasons.

Figure 16. Left: thermal sensation for the RBC scenario. Right: thermal comfort for the RBC scenario.

Figure 17 shows the ratings of thermal preference (Left) and clothing adjustments over the seasons (Right) for the RBC scenario. The thermal preference votes are very much aligned with the thermal sensation votes: The occupants would like the environment to be slightly warmer. The data on clothing shows the expected seasonal variation in clothing level, although these variations are often limited due to social reasons, hence, the clothing insulation varies even in Winter from 0.55 to 0.90.

Figure 17. Left: thermal preference for the RBC scenario. Right: clothing for the RBC scenario.

Figure 18 shows the ratings of local thermal sensation (Left) and local thermal comfort (Right) for the RBC scenario of the hands, arms, feet, head, and trunk. The data shows that the local thermal sensation and comfort is very similar for all body parts and also similar to the overall thermal sensation and comfort. This indicates that the indoor environment is very uniform, i.e. spatial gradients are limited. Hands, arms and the trunk are rated as thermally very uncomfortable by some subjects in Winter.

Figure 18. Left: local thermal sensation for the RBC scenario. Right: local thermal comfort for the RBC scenario. Number of surveys per season: 30 in Spring, 73 in Summer, 61 in Autumn, and 58 in Winter.

4.2 IEQ perception: Indoor air quality

4.2.1 Physical measurements

The CO₂ concentration was always below 950 ppm (550 ppm ΔCO₂ above outdoors – Category I EN 16798-1:2019) for an assumed outdoor CO₂ concentration of 400 ppm. Therefore, the air quality was within the limits during occupancy for all the investigated rooms suggesting no or minimum health risks as sufficient ventilation was provided for the investigated period.

4.2.2 Questionnaires

The questionnaire data is categorized per season to consider seasonal effects of IEQ variations. Figure 19 shows the ratings of acceptability of air quality (Left) and air freshness (Right) for the RBC scenario. On average, the IAQ is rated very good in Solarwind, in all seasons. However, the fairly large variance indicates substantial inter-individual differences. In turn, this may indicate that some people receive more fresh air than others, for example due to the positions of supply air vents.

Figure 19. Left: acceptability of air quality for the RBC scenario. Right: air freshness for the RBC scenario.

4.3 IEQ perception: Acoustical and lighting conditions

Figure 20 shows the ratings of acceptability of noise for the RBC scenario. On average, the noise is perceived as acceptable, but the large variation, peaking in Autumn, may indicate substantial inter-individual differences.

Figure 20. acceptability of noise for the RBC scenario.

Figure 21 shows the comfort ratings of light brightness (Left) and light color (Right) for the RBC scenario. Both are perceived as comfortable and the variations are rather small.

Figure 21. comfort rating for the RBC scenario of light brightness (Left) and light color (Right).

4.4 Self-perceived health effects

Figure 22 shows the ratings of severeness of headache (Left) and dryness of eyes (Right) for the RBC scenario. There is a clear seasonal effect of the reported severeness of headache which peaks in Winter. Both the mean and variation increase from Spring to Winter. The reported dryness of eyes does not show a strong seasonal effect, but the variation is large in all seasons, spanning the entire scale. This may be attributed to inter-individual differences and/or occupants' location in the open plan office, for example due to the positions of supply air vents.

Figure 22. Rating for the RBC scenario of headache (Left) and dry eyes (Right).

Figure 23 shows the ratings of severeness of nose (Left) and throat (Right) irritation for the RBC scenario. Nose irritation shows a slight increase towards Winter and the variance is large. Throat irritation peaks in Autumn.

Figure 23. Mean rating \pm SD for the RBC scenario of nose irritation (Left) and throat irritation (Right).

4.5 Self-perceived productivity effects

Figure 24 shows the ratings of alertness (Left) and fatigue (Right) for the RBC scenario. Alertness varies significantly over the seasons with minimum ratings in Winter. Fatigue is rather high in all seasons. Both alertness and fatigue are characterized by very large variances spanning the entire scale. Figure 25 shows the ratings of concentration, which shows very similar results.

Figure 24. Mean rating \pm SD for the RBC scenario of alertness (Left) and fatigue (Right).

Figure 25. Mean concentration \pm SD for the RBC scenario.

Figure 26 shows the ratings of task effort (Left) and task performance (Right) for the RBC scenario. Task effort shows no substantial seasonal effects and shows a rather dispersed image over all seasons, spanning the entire scale. Task performance also shows negligible seasonal effects and a smaller variance than task effort.

Figure 26. Mean rating \pm SD for the RBC scenario of Task Effort (Left) and Task Performance (Right).

5 Case study analysis: Líbeznice school, Czech Republic

5.1 IEQ and occupants' perception: Thermal environment

5.1.1 Physical measurements

The building had a model predictive control (MPC) implemented over the investigated years. Nevertheless, there was an initial MPC which was implemented only for heating mode, which was later upgraded for both heating and cooling on the 15th of May 2019. In the Líbeznice building, measurements took place in two classrooms, Neptune and Jupiter. The indoor environmental parameters measured were: air temperature (T_{air}), operative temperature (T_{op}), relative humidity (RH) and CO₂ concentration. However, due to several issues (e.g. destroyed sensors, malfunctions), the physical measurements were not available continuously for the two analysed years, 2018 and 2019.

Each space had multiple sensors which were part of the same stand, thus measuring at multiple heights. Since similar trends were observed between the values measured with differences only due to thermal stratification, only critical information is presented and discussed in this section, while further details are provided in the annex (Annex 2). In the graphs, the operative temperature value measured at a height of 0.6 m is shown. Additionally, details are provided for the operative temperature distribution for the heating and cooling periods. For the elementary school Líbeznice an occupancy schedule from 08:00 to 12:30 was taken from the timesheet provided. For the long-term evaluation, the limits defined were the ones recommended by standards EN16798-1:2019 and ASHRAE 55:2017 and summarized in chapter 3. The cooling and heating periods were defined according to the building operation, i.e. heating and cooling. Moreover, the IEQ limits selected from the standards were the ones recommended for offices and spaces with similar activity.

The resulting long-term evaluation of the indoor thermal environment for both Neptune and Jupiter is presented in Figure 27. During both years investigated, 2018 and 2019, the time outside the categories recommended by the standards for the operative temperatures was limited and close to zero in most instances. Overall, the building registered similar indoor environmental conditions in 2018 and 2019, with 40 to 60 % of the occupied time in Category I. According to the operative temperature distribution (Figure 28), during the heating season the operative temperature values varied over the entire range of Category III (19-25 °C), with similar distributions between the classrooms. Furthermore, around 50% to 80% of the data was situated in Categories I and II. During the cooling season, the operative temperature values were situated closer to the lower bounds recommended by the standards, with a higher standard deviation for Neptune than Jupiter. The values observed suggest that the spaces were generally cooler than recommended by the standards during the cooling season. Therefore, a higher set point during the cooling season could lead to a lower energy use and a better overall indoor thermal environment.

The operative temperature distribution shows no significant difference between the initial and the upgraded MPCs. Nevertheless, the implemented control could explain the difference between the deviations in the operative temperature from the recommended ranges presented in the standard. As the objective of the MPC was to minimize the thermal comfort violation and TABS power, the room temperature set point could have been relaxed (set to a lower/higher value still within the defined limits) for the benefit of reduced energy use. Additionally, in the Neptune room less outliers can be observed over the cooling season in 2019 compared to 2018 in the operative temperature distribution (Figure 28) which could indicate that the individual room MPC (upgraded MPC) accounted for differences between rooms.

With respect to drifts and ramps in the operative temperature, there were no visible issues as the indicators were within the limits presented by ASHRAE 55 for most of the occupied time (more than 95%). Nevertheless, some short term variations, for periods less than 1h were observed for Neptune as opposed to Jupiter. Overall, the

vertical temperature difference (VTD), between the head and ankles of a seated occupant was satisfactory with 94% and over of the occupancy time within category I (less than 2 K) of EN16798-1:2019 limits for both years. However, one of the sensors present in the classroom Neptune presented less satisfactory values in 2019, with 21% of time outside the recommended limits. Nevertheless, issues were frequently reported with the sensors present in the Libeznice building. Due to frequent sensor malfunctions and since the other stand present in the same classroom did not register a similar outcome, the less satisfactory VTD registered could be attributed to malfunctions with stand 6. Thus, generally the occupants were not subject to local thermal discomfort caused by abnormal vertical temperature difference.

Figure 27. Long-term indoor thermal environment evaluation, 2018 and 2019 – operative temperature (T_{op}) measured in Neptune and Jupiter at o.6.

No considerable difference was observed between the surface temperature of the ceiling covered or uncovered by the acoustic panel. The RH levels over the two years analysed were within Category I and II (between 25 and 60% - Category II) for approximately 80% to 90% of the occupied time and almost never above Category III. However, the time within Category III increased in 2019 compared to 2018, indicating RH values outside the recommended limits, however for a very short period of time (less than 5%).

Figure 28. Operative temperature (T_{op}) distribution during occupancy by classroom - cooling/heating season, 2018 and 2019, 0.6 m height.

5.1.2 Questionnaires

The questionnaire data is separately analysed for the two classrooms. Figure 29 shows the distribution of thermal sensation votes for Neptune and Jupiter classrooms. There is a clear difference between the two classrooms: whereas the majority of pupils rated the indoor temperature as neutral in Jupiter, 2/3 of the pupils in Neptune perceived the indoor temperature as too warm.

Figure 29. Distribution of thermal sensation ratings in Neptun (Left) and Jupiter (Right).

Figure 30 shows the distribution of thermal comfort votes for Neptun and Jupiter classrooms. There is a clear difference between the two classrooms: whereas the majority of pupils rated the indoor temperature as very comfortable or just comfortable in Jupiter, half of the pupils in Neptun perceived the indoor temperature as uncomfortable. This is partly visible in Figure 28 which shows higher air temperatures in the cooling season in classroom Neptun.

Figure 30. Distribution of thermal comfort ratings in Neptun (Left) and Jupiter (Right).

5.2 IEQ perception: Indoor air quality

5.2.1 Physical measurements

For the Libeznice building, a 400 ppm outdoor CO₂ concentration was assumed. Air quality was within the limits recommended by EN 16798-1:2019, with CO₂ concentrations lower than 950 ppm (550 ppm above outdoor CO₂ concentration, Category I) for more than 90% of the time. Moreover, the CO₂ concentration never reached values above Category II (800 ppm above outdoor CO₂ concentration). Thus, health risks were at a minimum as sufficient ventilation was provided.

5.2.2 Questionnaires

Figure 31 shows the ratings of air quality in Neptun and Jupiter classrooms. Again, there is a clear difference between the two classrooms: whereas only 15% of pupils rated the indoor air as stale in Jupiter, 50% of the pupils in Neptun perceived the indoor air as stale.

Figure 31. Distribution of ratings of the air quality in Neptun (Left) and Jupiter (Right).

6 Case study analysis: Ter Potterie elderly home, Belgium

6.1 IEQ and occupants' perception: Thermal environment

6.1.1 Physical measurements

The Ter Potterie building was under a rule base control (RBC) for the first two years, 2018 and 2019. In the first half of 2020, the RBC was still running. However, from July 2020, the control of the building alternated between the RBC and model predictive control (MPC). Therefore, the two periods with either RBC or MPC were analysed and presented separately for year 2020 for comparison. In the figures, the MPC operation is presented for approximately 63 days of 2020.

The same indoor environmental parameters were measured in the Ter Potterie building as for the other two buildings, namely air temperature (T_{air}), operative temperature (T_{op}), relative humidity (RH) and CO_2 concentration. Additional measurements consisted of surface temperatures of the radiator (T_{rad}), ceiling (T_{ceil}) and floor (T_{floor}). Measurements took place in a two-person apartment consisting of a bedroom (BC) and a living room (LC), two single rooms (SR53 and SR42) and a common space (LA).

Each space had multiple sensors which were part of the same stand, measuring at multiple heights and positions around the space. Since similar trends with differences only due to thermal stratification were observed between the measured values, only critical information is presented and discussed in this section, while further details are provided in the annex (Annex 3 – Physical measurement data Ter Potterie). As Ter Potterie is an elderly home, an occupancy schedule of 24/7 was assumed. Moreover, the limits for residential buildings were selected for the analysis for the IEQ recommended by standards EN16798-1:2019 and ASHRAE 55:2017 and summarized in chapter 3. For the analysis, the cooling and heating periods were defined according to the building operation, i.e. heating or cooling mode.

During RBC operation (2018, 2019, and first half of 2020), the time outside the categories recommended by the standards varied from 0 to maximum 39% in 2018 between the investigated spaces (Figure 32). Under the MPC operation (Figure 33), the time outside the categories recommended by the standards varied between 4% and 14%. Overall, a similar temperature distribution (Figure 34, Figure 35, and Figure 36) was registered between the three years and building operation (RBC and MPC) with the couple's living room (LC) in 2018 having the worse IEQ out of all the analysed spaces. Except for the LC, all rooms registered around 50 % or more time with the room temperature in Category I range. This was due to the high room temperature during the heating season and low room temperatures during the cooling season. More than 25% of the values, higher than the recommended upper limit (25 °C), were registered during the heating season (Figure 34, Figure 35, and Figure 36). During the cooling season of 2018 and 2019, 75% of the data was below 25.5 °C with values outside the recommended limits situated below the lower recommended bound of Category IV (21 °C). In 2020 however, less time with room temperatures below 21 °C were registered

According to Leliveld et al. [7]¹ the additional heating in winter but especially the extensive cooling in summer could be due to the control logic and temperature set point settings of the RBC. This is a typical operation of RBC which is doing its utmost best to prevent from over-heating in the summer time. Therefore, the control ends up overcooling. This would also be analogue for the heating season where a higher room temperature set point is set in order to avoid low temperatures. The former issue, overcooling, was reduced when the MPC was implemented, which represents an advantage of the new control. However, further investigation is required since less data points were registered during the cooling season under the MPC compared to the RBC.

¹ The full master graduation thesis has been attached as Annex 6 – MSc-graduation thesis: case study Ter Potterie

Figure 32. Long-term indoor thermal environment evaluation, 2018, 2019, and 2020, all under RBC operation – globe temperature (T_{gb}) inside the living area (LA), the bedroom (BC) and living room (LC), single room 53 (SR53) and single room 42 (SR42).

Figure 33. Long-term indoor thermal environment evaluation 2020, MPC – globe temperature (T_{gb}) inside the living area (LA), the bedroom (BC) and living room (LC), single room 53 (SR53) and single room 42 (SR42).

In all spaces, the vertical temperature difference between 1.1 and 0.1 (head and ankles of a seated occupant) was almost always less than 2 K, while the floor temperature was within 19 and 29 °C during most of the time (Table 1, Figure 39, and Figure 40). As both parameters were within the recommended values by EN 16798-1:2019, the occupants in the investigated rooms were not subject to local thermal discomfort from abnormal vertical temperature or warm/cool floors according to the standards. No significant issues were spotted with drifts or ramps in the air temperature within the building aside from a percentage of time (25 %) where the operative

temperature drifter more than 1.7 K within a period of 30 min in the single room SR₄₂ in 2018. The drift registered in SR₄₂ could be a consequence of window opening, allowing air to enter with a big temperature difference to the one in the space.

Table 17. Vertical temperature difference (VTD) and Floor temperature range (FTR) for Ter Potterie (2018 & 2019).

Criteria	Operation	Year	Value	Limits EN 16798-1
VTD	RBC	2018	99% and above CATI	$\Delta T_{1.1m,0.1m} \leq 2 \text{ K}$
	RBC	2019	100%	
	RBC	2020	100%	
	MPC	2020	100%	
FTR	RBC	2018	99% and above CATI	$19 \leq T_{\text{floor}} \leq 29$
	RBC	2019	96% and above CATI	
	RBC	2020	99% and above CATI	
	MPC	2020	100%	

Figure 34. Globe temperature (T_{gb}) distribution during occupancy by space - cooling/heating season, 2018, and 2019, RBC operation.

Figure 35. Globe temperature (T_{gb}) distribution during occupancy by space - cooling/heating season, 2020, RBC operation.

Figure 36. Globe temperature (T_{gb}) distribution during occupancy by space - cooling/heating season, 2018, 2019, and 2020, MPC operation

In the surface temperature distribution of the floor, ceiling, and radiator (Figure 37, Figure 38, Figure 39) it can be seen that the radiators were used even in warmer seasons. Both the globe temperature distribution (Figure 35) and surface temperature distribution of the radiator (for details on radiator position see chapter 2.1.3 and Leliveld [7]) could indicate that a higher operative temperature was generally preferred by the occupants of Ter Potterie. Therefore, the occupants adjusted their indoor thermal environment according to their needs. With respect to ceiling and floor temperature, the ceiling temperature was slightly higher than the floor surface temperature, indicating a normal temperature stratification. Finally, no significant difference was observed in the surface temperatures between the RBC and MPC scenarios.

Figure 37. Floor (FL), ceiling (CL) and radiator (R) temperature, communal living area (LA) and living room of the couple (LC), 2018, RBC.

Figure 38. Floor (FL), ceiling (CL) and radiator (R) temperature, communal living area (LA) and living room of the couple (LC), 2019, RBC.

Figure 39. Floor (FL), ceiling (CL) and radiator (R) temperature, communal living area (LA) and living room of the couple (LC), 2020, RBC.

Figure 40. Floor (FL), ceiling (CL) and radiator (R) temperature, communal living area (LA) and living room of the couple (LC), 2020, MPC.

For all years analysed, the relative humidity (RH) was within Categories I and II (between 25 and 60 %) according to EN16798-1:2019 for most of the occupied time (between 70% and 95% of the time depending on the year and space). Therefore, the RH levels were mostly within the recommended limits although no humidity control was employed in the Ter Potterie building. Moreover, as the Ter Potterie building is a residential building with an expected moderate activity level of less than 2 met and with temperatures less than 26 °C (at least 75% of the occupied time, Figure 35 and Figure 36) the influence of humidity was limited on the thermal sensation according to ISO 7730 (e.g. a 10% higher RH is felt as a 0.3 °C rise in the operative temperature).

6.1.2 Questionnaires

The questionnaire data is visualized in boxplots and categorized per season to consider seasonal effects of IEO variations. However, the graphs show no boxes due to the very low variance in the data of Ter Potterie. Moreover, a proper comparison between RBC and MPC mode was not possible due to the lack of questionnaire responses during MPC mode² (only 18 responses in Autumn). More questionnaire responses would be required to increase the statistical power of the comparison. Figure 41 shows the ratings of thermal sensation during the RBC scenario (blue) and MPC scenario (red). Irrespective of the season, the thermal sensation is by far mostly rated as neutral (>90% of votes). Only very few residents rate the indoor temperature as slightly cool or (slightly) warm, which votes are statistically considered as outliers (hence the presentation by only a line and dots as outliers).

Figure 41. Thermal sensation during the RBC (blue) and MPC (red) scenario. The numbers at the top indicate the number of surveys included in the analysis. A p-value < 0.05 indicates that the mean of the results of the RBC scenario is significantly different from the MPC scenario. The coloured notches in the boxes indicate the 95% confidence interval of the median.

Figure 42 shows the ratings of thermal comfort during the RBC scenario (blue) and MPC scenario (red). Irrespective of the season, the thermal comfort is predominantly rated as comfortable. Only very few residents rate the indoor environment as just comfortable or very comfortable, and also these votes are statistically considered as outliers.

² COVID-19 has played a crucial role in the delay of MPC implementation and conduction of questionnaires.

Figure 42. Thermal comfort during the RBC (blue) and MPC (red) scenario. The numbers at the top indicate the number of surveys included in the analysis. A p-value < 0.05 indicates that the mean of the results of the RBC scenario is significantly different from the MPC scenario. The coloured notches in the boxes indicate the 95% confidence interval of the median.

Figure 43 shows the distribution of thermal preference votes. In line with the thermal sensation votes, thermal preference is predominantly rated as 'no change'. Despite the thermal sensation was incidentally more rated on the warm side of the spectrum than on the cool side, residents indicated incidentally that their preference is more towards 'warmer' than 'cooler', which might be surprising, but combining the thermal sensation ratings with the comfort ratings shows that the residents perceived the warm sensation as comfortable, and hence, did not prefer a lower temperature. However, that being said, the number of deviations from neutral were negligible.

Figure 43. Thermal preference during the RBC (blue) and MPC (red) scenario. The numbers at the top indicate the number of surveys included in the analysis. A p-value < 0.05 indicates that the mean of the results of the RBC scenario is significantly different from the MPC scenario. The coloured notches in the boxes indicate the 95% confidence interval of the median.

Figure 44 shows the indicated clothing insulation of the subjects. The results reveal that clothing is not significantly different among seasons. The variance is even larger in the RBC scenario than in the MPC scenario, but this is likely the result of the limited number of responses in the MPC scenario. The elderly apparently do not adapt their clothing to the seasons.

Figure 44. Clothing during the RBC (blue) and MPC (red) scenario. The numbers at the top indicate the number of surveys included in the analysis. The coloured notches in the boxes indicate the 95% confidence interval of the median.

Figure 45 shows the ratings of local thermal sensation (Left) and local thermal comfort (Right) for the RBC scenario (blue) and MPC scenario (red) of the hands, arms, feet, head, and trunk. There are no differences between seasons and no differences between MPC and RBC control mode. Overall, occupants' local thermal sensation was predominantly neutral and their local comfort was predominantly rated as 'comfortable'.

Figure 45. Thermal sensation (Left) and thermal comfort (Right) during the RBC (blue) and MPC (red) scenario. The numbers at the top indicate the number of surveys included in the analysis. A p-value < 0.05 indicates that the mean of the results of the RBC scenario is significantly different from the MPC scenario. The coloured notches in the boxes indicate the 95% confidence interval of the median.

6.2 IEQ perception: Indoor air quality

6.2.1 Physical measurements

According to EN 16798-1:2019 the air quality was within the limits almost all of the time for all the rooms investigated. The CO₂ concentration was within CATI (less than 550 ppm above an outdoor concentration of 400 ppm) almost 100% of the occupied time. Therefore, health risks were at a minimum as sufficient ventilation was provided.

6.2.2 Questionnaires

The questionnaires are analysed for each month and presented as the relative distribution of the votes. Figure 46 shows the distribution of acceptance votes of air quality. The results show that residents are pleased with the indoor air quality as the majority indicated a high acceptance rate.

Figure 46. Distribution of acceptance votes of air quality for different months.

Figure 47 underlines this as the air is also perceived as very fresh.

Figure 47. Distribution of freshness votes of air quality for different months.

6.3 Self-perceived acoustical and lighting conditions

Figure 48 shows the acceptance rates of the acoustical conditions in the elderly home. The results clearly show a positive perception as almost all residents rate the acoustics as 'clearly acceptable'.

Figure 48. Distribution of acceptance votes of acoustical conditions for different months.

Figure 49 shows the acceptance rates of the lighting conditions in the elderly home. The results clearly show a positive perception as almost all residents rate the lighting conditions as 'clearly acceptable'.

Figure 49. Distribution of acceptance votes of lighting conditions for different months.

7 Case study analysis: Infrac offices, Belgium

7.1 IEQ and occupants' perception: Thermal environment

7.1.1 Physical measurements

Due to COVID-19, the IEQ measurements in Libeznice were discontinued and moved to Infrac. During the project, Infrac was upgraded from a case-study building to an MPC-demonstrator, and became the first office building with MPC. This allowed to indicate the indoor environmental impact of the two different controls in an office building. IEQ measurements were installed in Summer 2020 to complement the existing BMS data. During the investigated period, the occupation of the Infrac building was lower than normal due to the covid-19 pandemic.

In the Infrac building, measurements took place at the reception desk (S_3), and at two workspaces in the open-space office at the third floor (S_1 and S_2). The indoor environmental parameters measured were: air temperature (T_{air}), operative temperature (T_{op}), relative humidity (RH) and CO_2 concentration. The physical measurements were available in 2020 for two building control modes, rule-based control (RBC) and model predictive control (MPC), between which the building alternated.

Each space had multiple sensors which were part of the same stand, thus measuring at multiple heights. Since similar trends were observed between the values measured with differences only due to thermal stratification, only critical information is presented and discussed in this section, while further details are provided in annex (Annex 4 – Physical measurement data Infrac). In the graphs, the operative temperature value measured at a height of 0.6 m is shown. The indoor environment was categorized according to the heating, cooling and transition (between heating and cooling seasons) periods which were determined from the building HVAC operation, i.e. heating, cooling, or neutral (no heating/cooling, as documented in D4.11). Since Infrac is an office building, an occupancy schedule from 08:00 to 18:00 was assumed. For the long-term evaluation the limits defined were the ones recommended by standards EN16798-1:2019 and ASHRAE 55:2017 and summarized in chapter 3. Moreover, the IEQ limits selected from the standards were the ones recommended for offices and spaces with similar activity. Distinction was made between the building limits imposed on the indoor thermal environment depending on the building's operation, heating, cooling or neutral (transition) - Figure 50.

There was no noticeable difference in the indoor thermal environment between the period when the building was controlled using the RBC control and the one when the MPC control was implemented (Figure 51). The time outside the categories recommended by the standards for the operative temperatures was always zero with little to no occupied time classified as Category IV. The indoor thermal environment was mostly in Category II, the target indoor thermal environment for office buildings, with values between 74 to 84% for the RBC control, and between 71 to 85% for the MPC control. Nevertheless, the time within Category II, which was always less than 90% in both controls could also be due to the control logic applied. In the RBC, the room temperature set points could have been different than the ranges recommended by the standard due to occupant preferences. On the other hand, during the MPC operation, although within the defined comfort limits, the control may have modified the room temperature set point to minimize energy use.

Although not significantly worse, the operative temperature distribution (Figure 50) showed a higher variance in the operative temperature at the reception desk compared to the other investigated locations, especially during the cooling period. This could be due to the nature of the space which might present frequent door openings and changes in the number of occupants

Some drifts/ramps were registered during short periods of time (within 30 minutes) in the case of both controls, however for less than 2 % of the occupied time. Nevertheless, no visible issues were observed as no sudden or frequent fluctuations outside the allowed limits were present in the operative temperature for all locations

investigated. The vertical temperature difference between 1.1 and 0.1 (head and ankles of a seated occupant) was almost always less than 2 K (Table 18). Therefore, the occupants in the investigated rooms were not subject to local thermal discomfort from abnormal vertical temperature.

Figure 50. Operative temperature (T_{op}) distribution during occupancy by stand (S_1 , S_2 , S_3) under RBC (top) and MPC (bottom), 2020.

Figure 51. Long-term indoor thermal environment evaluation by stand (S1, S2, S3), a) RBC b) MPC, 2020.

Table 18. Vertical temperature difference (VTD) for Infrac during RBC and MPC operation.

Criteria	Year	Operation	Value	Limits EN 16798-1
VTD	2020	RBC	99% and above CATI	$\Delta T_{1.1m,0.1m} \leq 2 \text{ K}$
		MPC	98% and above CATI	

For both periods analysed, the RH was within Category II or better (between 25 and 60 %) of EN16798-1:2019 for most of the occupied time (more than 90%). The RH was slightly worse in the RBC case, as it registered 3% of the occupied time within Category III (between 20 and 70 %). However, as Infrac is an office building with an expected moderate activity level of less than 2 met and with operative temperatures less than 26 °C (Figure 50) the influence of humidity was limited on the thermal sensation according to ISO 7730 (e.g. a 10% higher RH is felt as a 0.3 °C rise in the operative temperature).

7.1.2 Questionnaires

The questionnaire data is categorized per season to consider seasonal effects of IEQ variations. Figure 52 shows the ratings of thermal sensation during the RBC scenario (blue) and MPC scenario (red). The variance of thermal sensation is rather small. The median is right at neutrality in the RBC case in Winter indicating that the indoor temperature is on average not biased. However, the thermal sensation in the MPC scenario is slightly lower, towards slightly cool, but this difference is statistically insignificant.

Figure 52. Thermal sensation during the RBC (blue) and MPC (red) scenario. The numbers at the top indicate the number of surveys included in the analysis. A p-value < 0.05 indicates that the mean of the results of the RBC scenario is significantly different from the MPC scenario. The coloured notches in the boxes indicate the 95% confidence interval of the median.

Figure 53 shows the ratings of thermal comfort during the RBC scenario (blue) and MPC scenario (red). In Winter, thermal comfort is rated on average slightly lower in the MPC scenario than in the RBC scenario, but still rated as 'just comfortable'. Moreover, the variance of thermal comfort votes is substantial indicating significant inter-individual differences: this could be due to differences in age, body composition, gender, or indicate effects of spatial differences due to air inlets for example. The latter seems more probable as this variance is more prominent in the MPC scenario than in the RBC scenario (while the group of test subjects was the same).

Figure 53. Thermal comfort during the RBC (blue) and MPC (red) scenario. The numbers at the top indicate the number of surveys included in the analysis. A p-value < 0.05 indicates that the mean of the results of the RBC scenario is significantly different from the MPC scenario. The coloured notches in the boxes indicate the 95% confidence interval of the median.

Figure 54 shows the ratings of thermal preference. As expected, subjects preferred the indoor temperature to be warmer in the MPC scenario in Winter. Effects are small but significant.

Figure 54. Thermal preference during the RBC (blue) and MPC (red) scenario. The numbers at the top indicate the number of surveys included in the analysis. A p-value < 0.05 indicates that the mean of the results of the RBC scenario is significantly different from the MPC scenario. The coloured notches in the boxes indicate the 95% confidence interval of the median.

Figure 55 shows the indicated clothing insulation of the subjects. The results reveal that clothing is not significantly different between control scenarios, but clothing insulation is slightly higher in Winter than in Autumn.

Figure 55. Clothing during the RBC (blue) and MPC (red) scenario. The numbers at the top indicate the number of surveys included in the analysis. The coloured notches in the boxes indicate the 95% confidence interval of the median.

Figure 56 shows the ratings of local thermal sensation (Left) and local thermal comfort (Right) for the RBC scenario (blue) and MPC scenario (red) of the hands, arms, feet, head, and trunk. In Winter, thermal sensation of the hands, arms, head and trunk was slightly, but significantly, lower in the MPC scenario. However, only the

drop of sensation of the arms was enough to induce a lower local thermal comfort (of the arms). Hence, whole body thermal comfort in Winter seemed to be driven by a lower thermal comfort in the arms.

Figure 56. Thermal sensation (Left) and thermal comfort (Right) during the RBC (blue) and MPC (red) scenario. The numbers at the top indicate the number of surveys included in the analysis. A p-value < 0.05 indicates that the mean of the results of the RBC scenario is significantly different from the MPC scenario. The coloured notches in the boxes indicate the 95% confidence interval of the median.

7.2 IEQ perception: Indoor air quality

7.2.1 Physical measurements

The CO₂ concentration was always below 950 ppm (550 ppm ΔCO₂ above outdoors – Category I EN 16798-1:2019) for both RBC and MPC controls for an assumed outdoor CO₂ concentration of 400 ppm. Therefore, the air quality was within the limits during occupancy for all the investigated locations suggesting no or minimum health risks as sufficient ventilation was provided for the investigated period.

7.2.2 Questionnaires

Figure 57 shows the ratings of acceptability of air quality (Top) and air freshness (Bottom) for the RBC scenario (blue) and MPC scenario (red). There are no significant differences between both scenarios and on average, air quality is rated as acceptable and fresh. However, the variance of the responses is rather large, which could indicate on spatial differences, for example due to positions of supply air vents.

Figure 57. Air acceptability (Top) and air freshness (Bottom) perception during the RBC (blue) and MPC (red) scenario. The numbers at the top indicate the number of surveys included in the analysis. A p-value < 0.05 indicates that the mean of the results of the RBC scenario is significantly different from the MPC scenario. The coloured notches in the boxes indicate the 95% confidence interval of the median.

7.3 Self-perceived acoustical and lighting conditions

Figure 58 shows the ratings of acceptability of noise for the RBC scenario (blue) and MPC scenario (red). There are no significant differences between both scenarios and on average, noise is rated as acceptable. However, the variance of the responses is large including unacceptable votes, which indicates that spatial differences could play a role (for example sitting next to someone who frequently calls). Besides, inter-individual differences like noise sensitivity could cause the variance.

Figure 58. Noise acceptability during the RBC (blue) and MPC (red) scenario. The numbers at the top indicate the number of surveys included in the analysis. A p-value < 0.05 indicates that the mean of the results of the RBC scenario is significantly different from the MPC scenario. The coloured notches in the boxes indicate the 95% confidence interval of the median.

Figure 59. Comfort ratings of light brightness (Top) and light colour (Bottom) during the RBC (blue) and MPC (red) scenario. The numbers at the top indicate the number of surveys included in the analysis. A p-value < 0.05 indicates that the mean of the results of the RBC scenario is significantly different from the MPC scenario. The coloured notches in the boxes indicate the 95% confidence interval of the median.

Figure 59 shows the comfort ratings of light brightness (Top) and light color (Bottom) for the RBC scenario (blue) and MPC scenario (red). As expected, there are no significant differences between both scenarios and on average, light brightness and light colour are rated as comfortable.

7.4 Self-perceived health effects

Figure 60 shows the ratings of severeness of headache (Top) and dryness of eyes (Bottom) for the RBC scenario (blue) and MPC scenario (red). Regarding headaches, there is no significant difference between the RBC and MPC scenario, moreover, variance of the votes is limited and results are concentrated to 'no headache'. Also, for dry eyes, there seems to be no difference between both scenarios, however, variance of results is substantial ranging between both extremes of the scale. Again, the positions of supply air vents may play a role.

Figure 60. Ratings of headache (Top) and dry eyes (Bottom) during the RBC (blue) and MPC (red) scenario. The numbers at the top indicate the number of surveys included in the analysis. A p-value < 0.05 indicates that the mean of the results of the RBC scenario is significantly different from the MPC scenario. The coloured notches in the boxes indicate the 95% confidence interval of the median.

Figure 61 shows the ratings of severeness of nose (Top) and throat (Bottom) irritation for the RBC scenario (blue) and MPC scenario (red). Throat and nose irritation seem to be lower in the MPC scenario, but the effects are statistically insignificant.

Figure 61. Ratings of nose irritation (Top) and throat irritation (Bottom) during the RBC (blue) and MPC (red) scenario. The numbers at the top indicate the number of surveys included in the analysis. A p-value < 0.05 indicates that the mean of the results of the RBC scenario is significantly different from the MPC scenario. The coloured notches in the boxes indicate the 95% confidence interval of the median.

7.5 Self-perceived productivity effects

Figure 62 shows the ratings of alertness (Top) and fatigue (Bottom) for the RBC scenario (blue) and MPC scenario (red). Figure 63 shows the ratings of concentration, which shows very similar results to alertness. The results reveal no significant differences in means and variances between both scenarios. Alertness, fatigue and concentration are all characterized by large variances, especially spanning the entire scale in Autumn.

Figure 62. Ratings of alertness (Top) and fatigue (Bottom) during the RBC (blue) and MPC (red) scenario. The numbers at the top indicate the number of surveys included in the analysis. A p-value < 0.05 indicates that the mean of the results of the RBC scenario is significantly different from the MPC scenario. The coloured notches in the boxes indicate the 95% confidence interval of the median.

Figure 63. Concentration ratings during the RBC (blue) and MPC (red) scenario. The numbers at the top indicate the number of surveys included in the analysis. A p-value < 0.05 indicates that the mean of the results of the RBC scenario is significantly different from the MPC scenario. The coloured notches in the boxes indicate the 95% confidence interval of the median.

Figure 64 shows the ratings of task effort (Top) and task performance (Bottom) for the RBC scenario (blue) and MPC scenario (red). There are no substantial differences between the scenarios, although task effort is very slightly higher in the MPC scenario, but the effect size is considered negligible. Task performance is assessed as high and task effort is mostly characterized by a large variance spanning the entire scale in autumn.

Figure 64. Ratings of Task Effort (Top) and Task Performance (Bottom) during the RBC (blue) and MPC (red) scenario. The numbers at the top indicate the number of surveys included in the analysis. A p-value < 0.05 indicates that the mean of the results of the RBC scenario is significantly different from the MPC scenario. The coloured notches in the boxes indicate the 95% confidence interval of the median.

8 Discussion and conclusions

8.1 Solarwind office

Questionnaires have been conducted over the course of two years, however, only for the RBC scenario as MPC implementation is due in 2021. The questionnaires in the RBC scenario reveal the following main findings.

Thermal sensation is biased to the cool side of the spectrum in all seasons. This is also reflected in thermal comfort which is also characterized by a large variance spanning the entire scale from 'very comfortable' to 'very uncomfortable'. Clothing is adjusted to the season, but shows very large variance. Local body parts show large variances over the seasons with increasing discomfort towards Winter of the hands, arms, head and trunk.

Air quality is assessed as acceptable and fresh on average, but large variances indicate spatial differences, for example possibly due to supply air vent positions.

Noise is rated as acceptable, but with large variance. On the contrary, light brightness and colour are rated on average as comfortable with very small variance.

Sick building syndromes such as nose and throat irritation, and dry eyes show very large variances spanning the entire scales, but headaches seem to appear mildly.

Productivity effects: Alertness shows a decreasing trend towards Winter and a large variance. Fatigue is significant in all seasons with large variances for each season. Concentration is on average high, but is also characterized by large variances in all seasons. Task effort indicates moderate effort on average with large variances peaking to 'strong effort'. However, task performance is rated as high on average with smaller variances.

The physical measurements matched the questionnaires, especially during the cooling season. Occupant votes indicated a preference to a slightly warmer indoor thermal environment all year round. However, the operative temperature was closer to the lower bounds of the Categories presented in EN 16798-1:2019 only during the cooling season, suggesting a slightly cooler indoor thermal environment than recommended. During the heating season, the operative temperature registered values over the entire range of Category II, 20 to 24 °C. Therefore, although within the recommended limits, a tighter control over the operative temperature might be preferred by the occupants, with values closer to the upper limit of Category II, 24 °C. The physical measurements registered also a normal thermal stratification, in sync with the limited spatial gradients suggested by the questionnaires.

The CO₂ concentration was within the limits of Category I. Therefore, sufficient ventilation was provided during occupancy, matching the average value obtained from the questionnaires which categorized the indoor air quality as acceptable and fresh. Relative humidity levels did not present a risk and are mostly within normal ranges for the occupied period. However, low levels could potentially be a contributing factor to dry eyes and throat irritation reported by some occupants.

8.2 Líbeznice elementary school

In the Líbeznice school the indoor thermal environment was mostly within the recommended limits of EN 16798-1:2019. The spaces in the building registered approximately 50% of the occupied time in Category I, which would satisfy a high level of occupant expectation. Moreover, the time outside the categories recommended by the standards for the operative temperatures was limited and close to zero in most instances. The operative temperature values measured throughout the cooling season suggest that the spaces are generally cooler than recommended, with values situated closer to the lower bounds of the standards. The measurements indicated that the occupants were not subject to local thermal discomfort caused by abnormal vertical temperature difference or drifts and ramps. Although the physical measurements show satisfactory thermal conditions, a substantial share of the pupils indicated that they perceived the indoor environment of the Neptun classroom as uncomfortably warm. The IEQ of the Jupiter classroom was mostly perceived as comfortable.

The presence of the acoustic panel did not influence the heat transfer between the TABS ceiling and the room. RH levels were within Category I and II (between 25 and 60%) for approximately 80 to 90 % of the occupied time and almost never above Category III. Air quality was within the limits recommended by EN 16798-1:2019, with CO₂ concentrations lower than 950 ppm for more than 90% of the time. Thus, health risks were at a minimum as sufficient ventilation was provided. However, this contradicts with the IAQ perception of the pupils in Neptun classroom: 50% perceived the indoor air as stale and 30% as slightly stale. In Jupiter classroom, the IAQ was perceived as better (15% stale/44% slightly stale).

8.3 Ter Potterie elderly home

In Ter Potterie although the MPC was active only for a limited period, no significant difference was observed in the IEQ measurement data between the RCP and MPC building operations. The globe temperature registered values higher than the recommended upper limit (25 °C) during the heating season and lower than Category IV (21 °C) limit during the cooling season for all years investigated. Moreover, except for the living room of the couple, all rooms registered around 50 % or more time with the operative temperature in Category I range. For the investigated rooms, the occupants were not subject to local thermal discomfort from abnormal vertical temperature or warm/cool floors nor abnormal drifts and ramps in the air temperature. The operative temperature during the heating season coupled with the surface temperature distribution of the radiator could indicate that a higher operative temperature than the recommended limits was generally preferred by the occupants of Ter Potterie.

For both years analyzed, the relative humidity (RH) was within Categories I and II according to EN16798-1:2019 for more than 91% of the total time. Finally, as indicated by the CO₂ concentration, sufficient ventilation was provided.

The residents in Ter Potterie elderly home perceived the indoor climate as very good. Interestingly, the questionnaire results show very little variation in the elderly's responses. A large majority found the thermal environment comfortable and did not want to change it. Moreover, a great majority rated the indoor air quality as clearly acceptable and perceived the air as fresh. Also, acoustical and light conditions were rated very high. Unfortunately, a proper comparison between RBC and MPC mode was not possible due to the lack of questionnaire responses during MPC mode (only 18 responses in autumn 2020).

8.4 Infrax office

On average, on a whole-body level, subjects perceived the indoor environment as slightly cool and their comfort level was slightly lower in the MPC scenario in Winter. Moreover, variance of thermal perception was larger in the MPC scenario. However, these differences were (just) not statistically significant. On the other hand, the same effects have been observed for local body parts, of which hands, arms, head and trunk did show statistically significant differences. Both differences of means and variance could not be explained by clothing behaviour. Note that although comfort was lower in the MPC scenario, it is still rated on average on the comfortable side of the spectrum (just comfortable).

Air quality was assessed on average as acceptable and fresh, without significant differences between RBC and MPC. However, the variance of the results was large indicating the spatial differences might play a role, e.g. due to fresh air supply positions.

Noise, light brightness and light colour were rated as acceptable and comfortable on average. Hence, there are no negative interaction effects explaining the lower thermal comfort in the MPC scenario in Winter.

All assessed health aspects do not differ between the RBC and MPC scenario. Sick building syndromes such as nose and throat irritation and headaches are very limited. However, dry eyes is characterized by a large variance in results spanning the entire scale, which indicates that some people substantially suffer from dry eyes and others not at all.

No noticeable differences were observed in the physical measurements of the indoor thermal environment between the RBC and MPC scenarios. Moreover, in both scenarios, the indoor thermal environment was classified as Category II, the target indoor thermal environment for office buildings for more than 80% of the time. This matched the average rating given by occupants, just comfortable. Nevertheless, discrepancies between the occupant votes and the physical measurements were observed. Occupant votes during winter, when heating is most likely to occur, pointed to a slightly cool indoor thermal environment in the MPC scenario. However, in the physical measurements, the operative temperature distribution was closer to the upper bounds of the Categories presented in EN 16798-1:2019 during the heating period in the MPC scenario than the RBC one, suggesting a slightly warmer indoor thermal environment than recommended.

The CO₂ concentration was within the limits of Category I. Therefore, sufficient ventilation was provided during occupancy in both RBC and MPC scenarios, matching the average value obtained from the questionnaires which categorized the indoor air quality as acceptable and fresh. Relative humidity levels did not present a risk and are mostly within normal ranges for the occupied period.

8.5 General

Overall, the indoor environmental quality was rated as medium according to Chapter 3 (ranges and limits according to EN 16798-1:2019) for all buildings investigated no matter the control employed. Deviations to moderate and low were observed for short periods of time in the thermal environment. However, these could also be because of the default control set points and the changes made by the occupants. Additionally, sufficient ventilation was supplied as the CO₂ concentration was always below the recommended limits and thus the indoor air quality was rated as high according to the same standard.

From the physical measurements at Infrax, it was determined that no significant differences were observed in the IEQ between the MPC and RBC scenarios. No significant issues were observed in the indoor thermal environment, vertical temperature difference, temperature fluctuations, and indoor air quality physical

measurements for the investigated period. However, the number of measurements were limited for the MPC scenario.

In general, the perception of IEQ (questionnaires) was rated as good and acceptable (thermal, air quality, light, acoustics). However, although indoor air quality was rated as fresh in general, in the school the pupils were dissatisfied with the indoor air quality in one of the two investigated classrooms despite the measurements revealed no issues regarding CO₂ concentrations. No clarification has been found for this deviation in the school and in general the scores regarding air quality were very positive for the tested buildings. Large variances were registered in terms of sick building syndromes (SBS) and productivity, but the median scores of the questionnaires revealed positive results for SBS and productivity related indicators.

Besides very small differences between RBC and MPC in thermal sensation and comfort of local body parts, all other outcomes do not reveal any significant differences between RBC and MPC. The general conclusion is that MPC is well capable of realising the same level of perception as RBC.

Thus, according to the standards and the feedback from the occupants the indoor thermal environment and comfort can still be improved by tuning the control objectives.

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Annex 1 – Physical measurement data Solarwind

Table 19. Sensor map Solarwind.

Room	Sensor	Height	Parameters measured
RA (reception area)	1AG	1.7 m	T _{air} , T _{gb} , RH
	2AG	1.1 m	T _{air} , T _{gb} , RH
	3AG	0.6 & 0.1 m	T _{air} , T _{gb}
	2		CO ₂
RO (reception office)	4AG	1.7 m	T _{air} , T _{gb} , RH
	5AG	1.1 m	T _{air} , T _{gb} , RH
	6AG	0.6 & 0.1 m	T _{air} , T _{gb}
	18		CO ₂
CO (corner office)	7AG	1.7 m	T _{air} , T _{gb} , RH
	8AG	1.1 m	T _{air} , T _{gb} , RH
	9AG	0.6 & 0.1 m	T _{air} , T _{gb}
	19		CO ₂
OP (open-plan office)	10AG	1.7 m	T _{air} , T _{gb} , RH
	11AG	1.1 m	T _{air} , T _{gb} , RH
	12AG	0.6 & 0.1 m	T _{air} , T _{gb}
	27		CO ₂

Figure 65. Long-term indoor thermal environment evaluation, Solarwind, 2018, 2019, and 2020 – operative temperature drifts and ramps measured in the reception area (RA), reception office (RO), corner office (CO) and the open-plan office (OP) at 0.6 m during occupancy.

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Figure 68. Globe temperature (T_{gb}) detail for 2018, 2019, and 2020 in the reception area (RA) at different heights.

Annex 2 – Physical measurement data Libeznice

Table 20. Sensor map Libeznice

Room	Sensor	Height	Parameters measured
Neptune	14AG	1.1 m	T _{air} , T _{gb} , RH
	15AG	0.6 & 0.1 m	T _{air} , T _{gb}
	17AG	1.1 m	T _{air} , T _{gb} , RH
	18AG	0.6 & 0.1 m	T _{air} , T _{gb}
	16AG	BMS height, opposite side	T _{air} , T _{gb} , RH
	26		CO ₂
Jupiter	20AG	1.1 m	T _{air} , T _{gb} , RH
	21AG	0.6 & 0.1 m	T _{air} , T _{gb}
	23AG	1.1 m	T _{air} , T _{gb} , RH
	24AG	0.6 & 0.1 m	T _{air} , T _{gb}
	13AG	BMS height, opposite side	T _{air} , T _{gb} , RH
	22		CO ₂

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Figure 73. Globe temperature (Tgb) detail for 2018 and 2019, Jupiter, at different heights.

Figure 74. Floor (fl) and ceiling (cl) surface temperature distribution by season for both classrooms, 2018 and 2019.

Annex 3 – Physical measurement data Ter Potterie

Table 21. Sensor map Ter Potterie.

Room	Sensor	Parameters measured	Sensor location
BC	31AG	T _{air} , T _{gb} , RH	Table between windows
(K138, bedroom of the couple)	32AG	T _{air} , T _{gb} , RH	Shelf between closet and bathroom
	17	CO ₂	
LC (K137, living room of the couple)	29AG	T _{air} , T _{gb} , RH	Shelf between closet and bathroom
	34AG	T _{air} , T _{gb} , RH	Shelf between closet and bathroom
	18	CO ₂	
SR53 (K153, single room)	19AG	T _{air} , T _{gb} , RH	Shelf between closet and bathroom
	22AG	T _{air} , T _{gb} , RH	On table
	31	CO ₂	
SR42 (K142, single room)	28AG	T _{air} , T _{gb} , RH	Shelf between closet and bathroom
	35AG	T _{air} , T _{gb} , RH	Table
	3	CO ₂	
LA (G108, living area)	25AG	T _{air} , T _{gb} , RH	
	26AG	T _{air} , T _{gb} , RH	
	27AG	T _{air} , T _{gb}	
	39	CO ₂	

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Figure 77. RH levels during occupancy, 2018, 2019, and 2020, Ter Potterie, RBC scenario.

Figure 78. RH levels during occupancy, 2020, Ter Potterie, MPC scenario.

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Figure 8o. CO₂ concentration levels during occupancy, 2020, Ter Potterie, MPC scenario.

Figure 81. Globe temperature (T_{gb}) detail for 2018, 2019, and 2020, bedroom couple (BC), at different heights.

Figure 82. Globe temperature (Tgb) detail for 2018, 2019, and 2020, single room 53 (SR53), at different heights.

Annex 4 – Physical measurement data Infracx

Room	Sensor	Parameters measured	Sensor location
S1 (workspace, open plan)	15AG	T _{air} , T _{gb} , RH	Level 3
	18AG	T _{air} , T _{gb} , RH	
	26	CO ₂	
	1	T _{surf}	
S2 (workspace, open plan)	21AG	T _{air} , T _{gb}	Level 3
	24AG	T _{air} , T _{gb}	
	22	CO ₂	
	2	T _{surf}	
S3 (reception desk)	14AG	T _{air} , T _{gb} , RH	Level 2
	17AG	T _{air} , T _{gb} , RH	
	20AG	T _{air} , T _{gb} , RH	
	23AG	T _{air} , T _{gb} , RH	
	3	T _{surf}	

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Figure 84. Relative humidity during occupancy, a) RBC and b) MPC, Infrac, 2020.

Figure 85. Drift/Ramp levels by stand in the a) RBC and b) MPC scenarios, Infrac, 2020.

Annex 5 Questionnaire templates

The questionnaire templates are included separately:

Annex 1A – Solarwind

Annex 1B – Líbeznice

Annex 1C – Ter Potterie

Annex 1D – Infrac

Annex 6 – MSc-graduation thesis: case study Ter Potterie

The master graduation thesis of Claudia Leliveld on IEQ measurements and analysis has been attached as a separate document.